

New Compounds of Gallium. Part I.

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Existing literature shows that only a few compounds of gallium are actually known. We have been fortunate in securing a tolerably large quantity of this rare metal and thus have been enabled to prepare many of its commoner inorganic and organic salts, which have hitherto been unknown.

A hydrate of the formula $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is known but we have been able to prepare another hydrate having the formula $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The former is obtained when the hydroxide is freshly precipitated from the nitrate by the action of sodium bicarbonate and is readily soluble in organic and inorganic acids. This compound, however, loses the property of dissolving in organic acids when it is kept overnight, and on drying in a vacuum desiccator has the composition $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ corresponding to $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. This property is shared by aluminium hydroxide also, which, when freshly prepared, dissolves easily in acids and in alkaline hydroxides, whilst $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is almost insoluble in dilute acids and alkalis.

Basic gallium acetate having the formula $5\text{Ga}(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_3, 2\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by Tchakirian (*Compt. rend.*, 1929, 189, 251) by adding 30% excess of acetic acid to a solution of a gallium salt neutralised with ammonium carbonate. Two basic acetates have been prepared, one having the same formula as the above compound but prepared by dissolving the freshly prepared hydroxide in acetic acid. The other compound was prepared by adding sodium acetate to a solution of gallium nitrate and possessed the formula,

A gallium tartrate is mentioned in a pharmaceutical paper (*Compt. rend.*, 1931, 192, 1142) but no mention has been made either of the composition or its method of preparation. We have prepared all the four tartrates of gallium, *d*, *l*, and *racemic* as well as the *meso* compound and have also determined the specific rotations of the *dextro* and the *laevo* compounds.

A normal oxalate of gallium of the formula $\text{Ga}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by Tchakirian (*loc. cit.*) by boiling a solution of gallium nitrate and oxalic acid in presence of sufficiently concentrated nitric acid to destroy the excess of oxalic acid, which otherwise dissolves the oxalate. We have prepared the same compound by dissolving freshly prepared gallium hydroxide in solution of oxalic acid. A basic oxalate of the formula $\text{Ga}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3, 3\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been obtained by adding sodium oxalate to a solution of gallium nitrate. The other compounds mentioned in this paper are new ones.

As regards analysis of the salts, organic salts were analysed by igniting them to the oxide and then weighing it. The initial heating was done very carefully in order to avoid charring as much as possible. In the case of inorganic salts, the hydroxide was first precipitated which was subsequently ignited to the oxide. In the case of soluble salts like the acid hypophosphite of gallium, it was dissolved in water and the solution boiled with solid hydrated sodium sulphite to precipitate the hydroxide (Dennis and Bridgeman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 1544). In the case of insoluble salts such as acid gallium phosphite, gallium phosphite and gallium hypophosphite, these were dissolved in hydrochloric acid and to the chloride solutions were added solid ammonium chloride and ammonia in excess. The solution was boiled till the excess of ammonia was removed when the precipitation of the hydroxide was completed as shown by Dennis and Bridgeman (*loc. cit.*). The filtrates did not contain any gallium and the precipitate no phosphorus compound.

The water was estimated by keeping a weighed quantity in an air oven heated to $100^\circ\text{-}110^\circ$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Gallium Hydroxides ($\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$).

Pure metallic Ga was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid by slow heat. The excess of nitric acid was evaporated to dryness. The nitrate was dissolved in water and the solution heated to boiling and to the hot solution, hot dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate was added drop by drop with constant stirring till the precipitation was complete. The white gelatinous precipitate was washed several times with hot water and then thoroughly dried in air between filter papers. (Found: Ga, 58.15; H_2O , 21.84. $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ga, 57.85; H_2O , 22.31 per cent).

The precipitated and washed hydroxide was kept in a vacuum desiccator until thoroughly dried when the hydrate with two molecules of water was obtained (Found: Ga, 62.76; H₂O, 15.63. Ga₂O₃, 2H₂O requires Ga, 62.50; H₂O, 16.07 per cent).

Gallium d, l, r, and meso-Tartrates.

Freshly prepared gallium hydroxide was just dissolved in aqueous solutions of the respective tartaric acids and solutions of the tartrates thus obtained were left in a vacuum desiccator for crystallisation. The salts were washed several times with alcohol in order to remove the free tartaric acids. All the tartrates were found to have the composition, Ga₂(C₄H₄O₆)₃, 4H₂O and were white crystalline substances, soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol and ether.

Gallium d-Tartrate. [Found: Ga, 21.30; H₂O, 10.79. Ga₂(C₄H₄O₆)₃, 4H₂O requires Ga, 21.34; H₂O, 10.97 per cent]. Sp. rotation in 1 dcm. tube = +20.3° and [M] = +133.1.

Gallium l-Tartrate. [Found: Ga, 21.03; H₂O, 11.05. Ga₂(C₄H₄O₆)₃, 4H₂O requires Ga, 21.34; H₂O, 10.97 per cent]. Sp. rotation in 1 dcm. tube = -20.0° and [M] = -131.2°.

Gallium Racemate. [Found: Ga, 21.07; H₂O, 11.17. Ga₂(C₄H₄O₆)₃, 4H₂O requires Ga, 21.34; H₂O, 10.97 per cent]. The salt was found to be optically inactive.

Gallium meso-Tartrate. [Found: Ga, 21.04; H₂O, 10.85. Ga₂(C₄H₄O₆)₃, 4H₂O requires Ga, 21.34; H₂O, 10.97 per cent]. The salt was found to be optically inactive.

Basic Gallium Acetate was deposited slowly as white hygroscopic micro-crystals from a solution of freshly prepared gallium hydroxide in dilute acetic acid, avoiding excess of the acid. The substance was repeatedly washed with alcohol in order to free it from the acid and then analysed by ignition to the oxide. The salt was found to be insoluble in water, alcohol and ether but soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. [Found: Ga, 38.30; H₂O, 6.45. 4Ga(CH₃CO₂)₃, 2Ga₂O₃, 5H₂O requires Ga, 38.51; H₂O, 6.18 per cent].

Basic Gallium Formate was obtained as a white crystalline substance by just dissolving the freshly prepared hydrate in dilute solution of formic acid and keeping it in a vacuum desiccator overnight. The salt was purified by washing with alcohol. The salt is insoluble in water, alcohol and ether but soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid.

[Found : Ga, 42.96; H_2O , 17.96. $Ga(HCO_2)_3$, Ga_2O_3 , $5H_2O$ requires Ga, 43.47; H_2O , 18.63 per cent]. The same salt was obtained by adding a solution of sodium formate to gallium nitrate solution, when a white precipitate was obtained. It was washed several times with hot water, dried and on analysis gave the identical composition. [Found : Ga, 43.94; H_2O , 19.15. $Ga(HCO_2)_3$, Ga_2O_3 , $5H_2O$ requires Ga, 43.47; H_2O , 18.63 per cent].

Normal Gallium Oxalate was prepared by just dissolving the freshly precipitated gallium hydroxide in a solution of oxalic acid. The solution on keeping in a vacuum desiccator yielded a white microcrystalline substance which was purified by repeated washing with a mixture of alcohol and ether. The salt is a hygroscopic, microcrystalline powder, readily soluble in water and moderately so in alcohol but insoluble in ether. [Found : Ga, 29.36; H_2O , 14.77. $Ga_2(C_2O_4)_3$, $4H_2O$ requires Ga, 29.41; H_2O , 15.12 per cent].

Gallium Citrate was prepared by dissolving the freshly precipitated hydroxide in dilute solution of citric acid, crystallised in a vacuum desiccator and purified by washing with alcohol. It is a white crystalline powder soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol and ether. [Found : Ga, 21.81; H_2O , 16.41; $Ga(C_6H_5O_7)$, $3H_2O$ requires Ga, 22.36; H_2O , 17.25 per cent].

Gallium Lactate was obtained in the same way by dissolving gallium hydroxide in dilute solution of lactic acid, crystallised and purified by washing with ether. Gallium lactate is a white microcrystalline powder soluble in water, moderately so in alcohol but insoluble in ether. [Found : Ga 18.65; H_2O , 10.31. $Ga(C_3H_5O_3)_3$, $2H_2O$ requires Ga, 18.76; H_2O , 9.65 per cent].

Gallium Malate was prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated gallium hydroxide in malic acid solution, crystallising in a vacuum desiccator and washing with alcohol. Gallium malate is a white crystalline substance soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol and ether. [Found : Ga, 23.67; H_2O , 9.75. $Ga_2(C_4H_4O_5)_3$, $3H_2O$ requires Ga, 23.72 ; H_2O , 9.15 per cent].

Acid Phosphite of Gallium was obtained by dissolving the freshly precipitated gallium hydroxide in dilute solution of phosphorous acid, evaporating to dryness in a vacuum desiccator and purified by washing with alcohol. The acid phosphite of gallium is a white crystalline powder, insoluble in water, alcohol and ether, but soluble in dilute

hydrochloric acid. [Found : Ga, 28.60; H₂O, 8.66. GaH₃(PO₃)₂, H₂O requires Ga, 28.11; H₂O, 7.22 per cent].

Normal Phosphite of Gallium.—When a solution of sodium phosphite was added to gallium nitrate solution, the white precipitate of the normal phosphite was obtained which was purified by washing with hot water and dried. The salt is insoluble in water, alcohol and ether, but soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. (Found : Ga, 41.55; H₂O, 11.62. GaPO₃, H₂O requires Ga, 41.91; H₂O, 10.78 per cent).

Acid Hypophosphite of Gallium was prepared exactly as the acid phosphite by dissolving the freshly precipitated gallium hydroxide in hypophosphorous acid. The substance was dried and washed with alcohol. The salt is a white powder, soluble in warm water, but insoluble in alcohol and ether. [Found : Ga, 34.34. GaH₁(PO₂)₂ requires Ga, 36.17 per cent].

Normal Hypophosphite of Gallium was obtained as a white precipitate by adding sodium hypophosphite to the solution of gallium nitrate. The precipitate was washed with hot water and dried. The salt is insoluble in water, alcohol and ether but soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. (Found : Ga, 45.49; H₂O, 11.18. GaPO₂, H₂O requires Ga, 46.35; H₂O, 11.92 per cent).

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